

Blended Learning in English Teaching and Learning

E'tibor Musulmonova

musulmonovaetibor@gmail.com

Uzbekistan State World Languages University

English language N3 Faculty-student

Scientific advisor

Dilrabokhon Akhmedjanova

daxmadjonova@gmail.com

Uzbekistan State World Languages University

ABSTRACT: This paper provides an overview of research related to the use of blended learning in English as a th language/foreign language context. Blended learning is a relatively new field that combines traditional educational approaches with distance and online learning. The use of blended learning is highlighted in recent study investigating the academic and societal benefits of this educational approach.

KEYWORDS: Blended learning, foreign language, effects of blended learning, ESL learner, ESL/ELF teachers, second language program,

INTRODUCTION: Blended learning, also known as hybrid learning, combines online and face-to-face instruction to create a flexible and effective learning environment. This approach has gained popularity in recent years, especially in language education, as it allows learners to engage with the language in various contexts and modes. In this article, we will explore the benefits of blended learning in English teaching and learning, and provide some practical tips for teachers and learners.

Specifically, Ghazizadeh and Fatemipour (2017) investigated the effects of blended learning on the development of reading comprehension in English learners in a quasi-experimental study. Specifically, this study aimed to investigate whether blended learning could be used to develop reading skills in 60 intermediate-level EFL learners from Iran. Participants were randomly assigned to two groups. An experimental group that received her hours of teaching and blended learning focused on reading skills, and a control group that received her hours of a more traditional approach to teaching English. Two groups were tested before and after treatment to determine the reading level of 55,555 learners. After comparing her two groups using a t-test, the researchers found that the use of mixed learning had a statistically significant positive effect on reading comprehension in EFL learners. discovered. In other words, Ghazizadeh and Fatemipour (2017) argue that the use of blended learning with language learners has a direct impact on improving language learners' reading skills. Based on their findings, the researchers also found that blended learning

accelerated the learning process and could be successfully used in English reading classes. Similarly, Adas and Bakir (2013) examined the use of blended learning strategies in developing writing skills in EFL learners. Specifically, the purpose of this study was to determine whether blended learning could be an effective strategy in improving students' overall writing performance. The study involved 60 EFL learners from 55,555 Palestinian universities. Students were divided into two groups, one group was taught English writing using a traditional face-to-face approach and the other group was taught using a mixed learning model. At the end of the 55,555-hour teaching period, the researchers found that the group taught using blended learning performed better in writing than the other groups. In other words, the use of blended learning contributed to the development of writing skills in her EFL learners who participated. The researchers concluded that using blended learning improved many aspects of participants' writing, including grammar, spelling, punctuation, and paragraph coherence. Additionally, Grurovic (2011) investigated the use of blended learning in the context of ESL. Using the Neumeier (2005) blended learning framework, this study determined how blended learning would be used in ESL classes and how both face-to-face and distance learning would be integrated. This study was conducted in speaking and listening classes as part of the Intensive English Program in the United States. Participants were 19 ESL students and 1 English teacher. Study method included observations of language instruction, interviews with students, and interviews with teachers to examine the effectiveness of this learning model. The results show that blended learning can be successfully used to effectively teach any language skill. Both teachers and students shared positive views and attitudes towards incorporating Blended Learning into their English lessons. They believed that the use of online instruction would complement traditional methods and enhance the language learning process of their students. The researchers concluded that blended learning can be used effectively for teaching English in foreign/second language programs. In another study, Shih (2010) also investigated the use of blended learning approaches for teaching English courses. In particular, this study aimed to design a blended learning environment utilizing educational blogs with ESL learners. Forty-four university ESL learners participated in this study. To do this, several research methods were used investigate the impact of mixed learning modes, including a student satisfaction survey, 55,555 feedback from teachers and students, and student reflection and interviews. As a result of research, we found that using blended learning mode in video-based blogging brings many benefits, including: B. Improve students' speaking skills, foster autonomy and cooperation, and enhance the learning process. Shih (2010) states that one of his

benefits of the blended learning approach is that it improves not only the student's speaking skills, but also the student's other language skills such as grammar, pronunciation, facial expressions, and eye contact. I explained. However, other studies have shown that the use of blended learning does not necessarily directly affect language skills. For example, Tosun (2015) investigated the effects of using blended learning approaches in teaching English vocabulary. The study also investigated English learners' perceptions of blended learning when learning English vocabulary. The study involved her 40 students attending two of his classes in the Intensive English Program in Turkey. The 55,555 participants were divided into her two groups. An experimental group that learned the target vocabulary through her blended learning approach and a control group that learned the same vocabulary using conventional (face-to-face) teaching methods. At the end of the lesson, both groups' vocabulary knowledge was tested. Results indicated that although students were satisfied with using blended learning as a teaching strategy, the use of blended learning strategies did not have a positive impact on students' vocabulary skills. Tosun (2015) said their findings were inconsistent with many previous studies that have linked the use of blended learning to language skill development. Tosun added that the only possible explanation for these results is the short duration of the study. Overall, research in the context of ESL and EFL shows that blended learning can be effectively used to develop language skills in English learners. The research investigated suggests that language teachers can use her blended learning as a teaching model to develop various skills such as reading, writing, speaking, and vocabulary.

CONCLUSION.

Blended learning is an educational strategy that combines both traditional face-to-face and online education in one setting. A growing trend in the era of technological development. Blended learning is a promising idea that has brought together many important areas such as educational methodology, educational technology, and online teaching and learning. The use of blended learning in the context of ESL/EFL has received considerable attention as a method of teaching and learning English. Studies show that using blended learning alone instead of traditional classroom and online teaching approaches offers many benefits not only for student learning but also for the learning environment. These benefits include enhancing the English learning process, developing language skills, and improving the English learning environment. Despite these advantages, some challenges associated with the use of blended learning can arise. However, the literature investigating the problems teachers face when using blended learning approaches in an ESL/EFL context is lacking. Further research is needed to

explore the perspectives of ESL/EFL teachers on the challenges they face in using blended learning in teaching and learning English.

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